

COMPARISON OF A DBA SEQUENCE IN A GENERIC iPWR BETWEEN MELCOR AND ASTEC CODES

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ABSTRACT

In view of the possible licensing needs of Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), due to the envisaged short-term deployment, the international scientific community has focused his interest in characterizing the SA integral codes capabilities in simulating SMR behavior during postulated Design Basis Accident (DBA), Beyond Design Basis Accident (BDBA) and Severe Accident (SA) scenarios. One type of SMR is the integral Pressurised Water Reactor (iPWR), which is ready to be licensed as a new build because they start from the well-proven and established large-LWR technology including moderate evolutionary design modifications to increase the inherent safety of the plant. However, despite the inherent increase of the safety of the plant with the adoption e.g. of passive safety systems and integral configuration, a sound demonstration of iPWR ability to address SA should be carried out along a safety review process. Therefore, in order to speed-up iPWR European licensing process, the Horizon Euratom project “Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accident” (SASPAM – SA), coordinated by ENEA (Italy), investigates the applicability and transfers of the operating large LWR knowledge and know-how to iPWRs in view of SA and Emergency Planning Zone (EPZ) European licensing analyses needs. In this framework, a code-to-code benchmark exercise between MELCOR and ASTEC integral codes has been conducted by ENEA, considering a generic 300 MWe iPWR. Due to the integral configuration a SBLOCA event has been considered; in particular a guillotine break of one Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) line has been selected as Postulated Initiating Event (PIE) of the DBA sequence. The main goal of the work is to evaluate the capability of the codes in simulating the dominant thermal-hydraulic phenomena in a generic iPWR design and assess the possible encountered discrepancies.

KEYWORDS

SASPAM-SA; SMR; DBA; MELCOR; ASTEC

1. INTRODUCTION

Integral Severe Accident (SA) codes, such as ASTEC [1][2] and MELCOR [3][4], are widely used to simulate the behavior of Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs) in transient conditions allowing to characterize the thermal-hydraulic and degradation phenomena that take place in postulated SA. Nowadays, the international nuclear community working on Deterministic Safety Analysis (DSAs) in the SA domain is currently interested to investigate the applicability of these codes to light water Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) designs due to their envisaged deployment and the consequent licensing needs. In particular, integral Pressurized Water Reactor (iPWR) are ready to be licensed as new builds because they start from the well-proven and established large Light Water Reactor (LWR) technology, incorporate their operational plant experience/feedback, and include moderate evolutionary design modifications to increase the inherent safety of the plant. Example of evolutionary modifications are the use of integral RPV (where is located the core, a compact Steam Generator – SG – and the pressurizer – PRZ –), and the use of passive safety systems for, e.g., high and low pressure injection, removing the residual core power through passive heat exchanger immersed in pool, containment cooling and pressure suppression, etc. Therefore iPWRs, as the advanced designs, are in general characterized by common features with the current operating large-LWR and by other specific features typical of their inherent evolutionary designs, providing safety advantages that reinforce the first three levels of the DiD principle. However, even if a plant is designed with advanced inherent features (through the reinforcement of the 1,2,3 DiD levels) allowing a reduction of the Core Damage Frequency (CDF), independent features for preventing and mitigating a SA sequence have to be included in its design (DiD level 4) together with the offsite emergency response (DiD level 5). Therefore, some scenarios that could lead to SAs need to be postulated and deterministically studied (More detailed information's in [7]). Therefore, it is necessary to assess the capability of internationally recognized SA code to describe the behaviour of the most promising iPWR designs during SA scenarios and to predict the resulting radiological impact on- and off-site. Therefore, state-of-art SA codes should be proven able to simulate these advanced features and the related phenomenology [5][6]. In the present study, a code-to-code benchmark has been conducted to investigate the integral SA codes capabilities in simulating the main thermal-hydraulic phenomena occurring in a generic iPWR design during a DBA sequence. The aim of the activity is to gain first insights about the possible differences in predicting iPWR typical phenomena between the codes ASTEC and MELCOR. ASTEC is a European code developed by the Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (IRSN); MELCOR is a non-European code developed by Sandia National Laboratories (SNL) for the United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission (USNRC). Subsequently, a validation against experimental could be needed to characterize the phenomena that need a further investigation, in term of qualitative and quantitative accuracy, reducing uncertainties in the results. The present activity has been conducted in the framework of the Horizon Euratom “Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accident” (SASPAM-SA) project [8,9,10], coordinated by ENEA (Italy), having as a target to assess the capability of internationally recognized European and Non-European computational tools (largely used in Europe)¹ to describe the behaviour of some promising iPWR designs during SA scenarios

¹In order to maximize the knowledge transferability and impacts of the project two generic design-concepts, characterized by different evolutionary innovations in comparison with larger operating reactor, have been selected for the analyses: a) iPWR characterized by a submerged containment and electric power of about 60 MWe, called design 1; b) iPWR characterized by the use of several passive systems, a dry containment and an electric power of about 300 MWe, called design 2. These two generic reactor concepts include the main iPWR design features, considered in the most promising designs ready to go on the European market, allowing to assess in a wider way the capability of codes (SA and CFD) to simulate the SA phenomena typical of iPWR. It is not the project's objective to assess the generic reactor designs selected but, based on the project findings, allow a more general statement on the

and to predict the resulting radiological impact on- and off-site. A generic iPWR 300 MWe reactor has been adopted as in this analysis. It is characterized by a dry containment and the use of different passive systems. Since the aim of the activity is to test the capability of ASTEC and MELCOR code in reproducing the behavior of different passive safety systems and their interaction in a SMR configuration, in order to analyze codes capability in a wider way, the following passive systems have been considered (Figure 1)²: decay heat removal, primary automatic depressurization, high and low pressure safety injection, containment pressure suppression, flooding of the Reactor Cavity (RC). Considering the characteristics of the selected design, a generic International Reactor Innovative and Secure (IRIS) SMR type has been considered in this study as reference to develop the input-deck for both codes, without using proprietary data. The main geometric data of the reactor was determined by scaling the available data of the SPES-3 experimental facility [12][13] as well as by engineering evaluation of from public general data available [11]. The ASTEC and MELCOR input-decks have been employed to simulate the same DBA sequence initiated by the Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) line double-ended guillotine break, already studied in past activities [14][15]. The reason why it has been selected this scenario is because it is the most challenging SBLOCA transient that can happen due to the lower elevation.

Figure 1 – Scheme of the generic iPWR design with the passive safety systems.

2. GENERIC iPWR DESIGN AND CODES NODALIZATION DESCRIPTION

code's applicability to currently favored designs under postulated SA condition. No PSA considerations will be done in the project due to the generic nature of the reactor concept considered, then the scenarios identified will be characterized in terms of severity but not in terms of probability.

² Passive systems are, on the one hand, an advanced solution to increase the inherent safety of the plant (e.g., there is no need of pumps), on the other hand a) they require extensive investigation for assessing the functional failure related to the thermal-hydraulic phenomena driving the operation of the systems and assess the related uncertainties, b) may still need an active initiation, and c) are characterized by very limited operational experience (to have more detailed information [7,19]). Considering this, the impact of the operation of passive systems on postulated severe accident progression is a novel topic and needs to be assessed. Considering this, the specific assessment of the code capability to simulate passive systems phenomenology is crucial. In fact, in LW-SMR reactors the BDBA/SA scenarios evolution depend from the postulated partial or total not operation of passive systems (e.g. postulate the failure of passive system valve activation). Therefore, it is necessary to analyse the capability of SA codes to predict the main thermal-hydraulic phenomena involved in the passive mitigation strategy of LW-SMR in order to adequately apply them for the design of accident management's strategy (first phase of a SA is only dominated by T-H phenomena, then in-vessel is affected by thermal-hydraulic phenomena).

2.1. Description of the generic iPWR design

In the generic iPWR considered in this study, all the RCS components, such as the PRZ, SGs and the Reactor Coolant Pumps (RCPs), are integrated into the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV), as shown in **Figure 1**. After flowing through the core, the primary coolant crosses the riser region (surrounded by the extended core barrel) and at the top of the riser is directed radially into the upper annular plenum, which houses the RCPs' suction region. RCPs pump the coolant inside the correspondent SGs module, where the selected iPWR design envisages the use of helical-coil SGs. After transferring the thermal power to the secondary fluid, the primary coolant flows downward along the annular downcomer region surrounding the core to the Lower Plenum (LP) and then returns up to the reactor core. The passive mitigation strategy of this iPWR design is based on several passive systems which carry out different safety functions: natural circulation in the RPV (Riser-Downcomer -RI-DC-), decay heat removal (Emergency Heat Removal System -EHRS-), primary automatic depressurization (Automatic Depressurization System -ADS-), high pressure safety injection (Emergency Boration Tanks -EBTs-), low pressure safety injection (Long-term Gravity Make-up System -LGMS-), containment pressure suppression (Pressure Suppression System -PSS- tanks), flooding of the Reactor Cavity (RC). The passive safety systems are schematized in **Figure 1**. The passive mitigation strategy envisages in case of one of the two Direct Vessel Injection (DVI) lines guillotine break and the role played by each safety system in the passive mitigation strategy are described in the following as well as in [14][15].

2.2. MELCOR nodalization description

MELCOR [3][4] is a fully integrated SA code able to simulate the thermal-hydraulic phenomena in steady and transient condition and the main SA phenomena characterizing the RPV, the RC, the containment, and the confinement buildings typical of LWR. The estimation of the source term is obtained by MELCOR code as well. The code is based on the "control volume" approach. MELCOR can be used with the Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package (SNAP) [16] to develop the nodalization and for the post processing of data by using its animation model capabilities. MELCOR has a modular structure and is based on packages. Each package simulates a different part of the transient phenomenology. The MELCOR code version used for this analysis is MELCOR v2023. The nodalization has been developed using SNAP, with a trade-off between the computational time and a detailed prediction capability of the transient thermal-hydraulic, as well as core degradation, phenomenology.

Figure 2 – MELCOR CVH nodalization.

The RPV is divided in different hydraulic regions including the LP, the reactor core, the core by-pass, the riser, the Upper Plenum (UP), the SGs and the downcomer. They have been modelled using the CVH and

FL MELCOR packages, simulating the thermal-hydraulics behavior of the system, and coupled with the HS package, modelling the heat transfer between the CVH Control Volumes (CVs). The two passive systems lines have been modelled separately. Each line includes the EBT, the PSS, the PSS-vent and the LGMS systems. To simplify the model, the SGs have been modelled as an equivalent one, with four CVH CVs on the primary side and eight CVs on the secondary side. The reactor core has been modelled by a single hydraulic CVH CV coupled with the correspondent reactor core model of the COR package. The reactor core and LP nodalization in the COR package is characterized by sixteen axial levels and six radial rings. The containment region has been modelled with one CVH volume of the RC, coupled with the correspondent CAV MELCOR package, and with one CVH volume for the DW region, thermally coupled with the environment CVH volume. In **Figure 2**, a schematic view of the MELCOR CVH and FL nodalization is presented.

2.3. ASTEC nodalization description

The ASTEC [1][2] code, aims at simulating an entire SA sequence in nuclear water-cooled reactors from the initiating event through the release of radioactive elements out of the containment. ASTEC includes several coupled modules that can deal with the different SA phenomena: thermal-hydraulics in the reactor system, core degradation and melt release, fission product release and transport, ex-vessel corium interaction, aerosols behavior and iodine chemistry in the containment, etc. The generic iPWR ASTEC model has been developed using the code version ASTEC v3.1 (study carried out with ASTEC V2, IRSN all rights reserved, [2024]). The code module CESAR is dedicated to the thermal-hydraulics of the reactor coolant system. It has been used for detailed nodalizing the upper part of the RPV, the secondary system (steam line, feedline and SGs), and most of the passive safety systems (i.e., DVIs, EBTs, PSS, LGMS, EHRS). A generic scheme of the ASTEC CESAR nodalization is reported in **Figure 3** (a). A 6-channels core model has been developed with ICARE module (4 core channels + 1 bypass channel and 1 downcomer channel), for the bottom-RPV and the core nodalization. The core internals have been realized as 2D components by employing the ICARE dedicated structures, and the models for the simulation of in-vessel core degradation phenomena are activated. The CPA module of the code, usually in charge of containment thermal-hydraulic modelling, has been used to model the DW of the continent. The dedicated insertion model of CPA is used to model the QT suppression system. The RC has been modelled with a ERVC pipe structure of CESAR to be thermally coupled with the external vessel structure of ICARE, as schematically described by **Figure 3** (b).

Figure 3 – ASTEC CESAR nodalization [12]

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE TRANSIENT

To develop the code-to-code benchmark here presented, a DBA transient progression has been considered with the availability of all the emergency passive safety systems. The scenario under investigation is a Loss Of Coolant Accident (LOCA); the Postulated Initiated Event (PIE) is the double-ended guillotine break of one of the two DVI lines. The loss of primary coolant, caused by the opening of the break, results in a single and two-phase blowdown with the consequently RPV depressurization. Due to the

pressurization of the containment, a steam-gas mixture moves from the DW to the PSS through the PSS-vent lines increasing the pressure of the PSS-LGMS system. The RC is gradually filled with the primary coolant from the break and with the steam condensed on the metal internal surface of the DW. Once the containment high-pressure set-point is achieved, the S-Signal initiates the reactor SCRAM; due to this the isolation of the secondary side of SGs and the opening of two of the four EHRS loops occur³. The isolation of the SGs determines the increase of the secondary pressure. A natural circulation in the EHRS system begins, permitting the transfer of the thermal power to the water inside the RWST tanks, the cooling of the RPV and its depressurization. The low level of the coolant in the PRZ triggers the RCPs coast-down and the following automatic opening of the RI-DC check valves. These valves enable natural circulation at a lower RPV level permitting to the primary coolant to flow through a shorter path and bypassing RCP suction plenum. The LM-Signal (LOCA Mitigation) is then triggered when the PRZ pressure reaches the low pressure set-point. It determines the opening of the ADS stage-1, the start of the injection by EBTs and the opening of the two remaining EHRS system loops. The ADS stage-1 allows the steam dump from the PRZ to the QT, contributing to the RPV depressurization and acceleration of the equalization between primary and the DW pressures. The EBTs discharge borated cold water inside the RPV through the DVI lines by gravity. Whereas the intact DVI line releases water into the RPV, the broken one discharges water into the RC. At the primary and DW pressure equalization, the low RPV-DW differential pressure signal activates the LGMSs. The LGMS tank of the intact loop discharges water in the RPV by the intact DVI line while the LGMS of the broken loop discharges water in the RC. After this point, because of the steam condensation in the DW and the heat removed due to the EHRS system, the pressure in the DW decreases below the PSSs pressure. Consequently, the water inside the PSSs is forced upward through the PSS vent pipes, until filling the RC after dropping from the top end of the PSS vent pipe. This water head inside the PSS vent-pipe maintains a differential pressure between the LGMS (equal to PSS) and RPV (equal to DW) throughout the depressurization phase, which improves the LGMS water injection. Steam circulation between RPV and DW is enabled by the ADS stage-2 valves opening upon reaching the LGMS low water mass signal. The water in the RC keeps the core filled during the long-term cooling phase. The heat losses thorough the DW metal walls to the environment and the power extracted by the EHRS systems allow the cooling down of the core.

4. ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

4.1. Steady-state calculations

A steady-state analysis has been conducted to reach the initial reference conditions before the beginning of the transient. The values of the main steady-state parameters were compared with reference steady-state values collected and consolidated in the SASPAM-SA project and reported in [20]. Both codes have a discrepancy of less than 3% compared to the reference data. To characterize the results of the codes during the steady-state, the pressure distribution along the RPV primary side has been compared; in particular a maximum of 0.2% error is observed.

4.2. Analysis of the transient evolution

The simulation of the DBA has been investigated for 50000 s. The Start Of the Transient (SOT) has been considered at $t = 0$ s, with the postulated double-ended guillotine break of one of the two DVI lines. After the break, the transient is initially driven by the blowdown of the RPV. The high containment pressure set-point initiates the S-signal, which activates the SCRAM, the isolation of the SGs and the opening of the EHRS loops. Due to the SGs isolation, the SCS temporary pressure increases in both the codes. At approximately 122 s after the SOT in MELCOR and 65 s in ASTEC, the Low PRZ level signal is initiated, with the following primary pumps coast-down and RI-DC valves opening. After this phase, the mass flow rate is sustained only by natural circulation inside the RPV. The low PRZ pressure signal determines,

³ For the analyses presented in the paper, because of the nodalizations structure (only one equivalent EHRS), the logic is simplified and only one actuation of EHRS is considered.

around 148 s in MELCOR and 158 s in ASTEC, after the SOT, triggering the opening of ADS Stage-1 and EBTs. Observing the mass flow rate through the break and the cumulative mass shown in **Figure 4**, at the SOT both the codes predict the same behavior and initial peak. The opening of the ADS 1 is practically at the same time for both (respectively 166 s ASTEC and 167 s MELCOR) and, moreover, the mass flow rate predicted by the two codes is qualitative and quantitative well represented and comparable in this first phase.

Figure 4 – Break mass flow rate and cumulative discharged mass.

Figure 5 – Decay power generated in the core, the power transmitted to the primary coolant from the core, the power transmitted from the primary system to the secondary system and the power transmitted from the secondary system to the EHRS.

Figure 6 – Pressure behavior of the primary system and the DW

Due to that, the two codes predict an increasing of the depressurization rate in the first seconds after the ADS 1 opening. The primary pressure calculated by the two codes is comparable along the subcooled blowdown. The activation of the EHRS system allows the heat removal from the reactor core by natural

circulation, which is predicted in both codes; **Figure 5** shows the decay power generated in the core, the power transmitted to the primary coolant from the core, the power transmitted from the primary system to the secondary system and the power transmitted from the secondary system to the EHRS. While in MELCOR the EHRS power peak is about 100 MW, the ASTEC data present a higher peak of about 140 MW. Moreover, during the first 1000 s of the transient, the EHRS system removed power in ASTEC is greater than in MELCOR. This, coupled with the higher break mass flow rate in ASTEC, determines that, at about 800 s, the primary system depressurization in ASTEC is faster than MELCOR (**Figure 6**). The faster pressure decrease in ASTEC primary side determines a faster pressure increase in the DW with a consequent faster pressure equalization between the primary and the DW. It is to note that due to the higher energy removed from EHRS in ASTEC calculation, saturated blowdown is reached before in MELCOR than in ASTEC (MELCOR at 223s and ASTEC at 913s); this quantitative difference determines a higher mass flow rate in ASTEC in comparison with MELCOR, as shown in figure **Figure 4**. Observing **Figure 6**, the first ASTEC pressure equalization occurs at 1584 s while MELCOR predicts the equalization at 2000 s. Pressure equalization is followed by the increase of the DW pressure; this is due to the energy removed by the EHRS that contributes to depressurize the RPV in comparison with the DW. This phenomenology determines the stop of the break flow rate in both the codes. MELCOR code, between 2000 s (1st pressure equalization) and 3315 s (2nd pressure equalization), does not predict water injection from the break to the cavity (**Figure 4**). After the second equalization the pressure in the RPV becomes higher again and, consequently, the break flow rate start again. ASTEC code reaches the 2nd pressure equalization (**Figure 4** and **Figure 6**) at 6006 s, predicting a delayed restart of water injection through the break from the primary side to the cavity. Therefore, both codes predict the same phenomenology with different timing. Another important phenomenon to underline is the reverse flow through the break, that should take place when the level in the cavity reaches the broken DVI line and the DW pressure is higher than RPV pressure. The phenomenon is strictly related to the cavity level, **Figure 7** and **Figure 8** for ASTEC and MELCOR respectively; indeed both codes predict a) an increase of the break massflow rate after the 2nd pressure equalization, b) a decrease of the massflow rate when the level in the cavity reach the DVI line (respectively 6600 s ASTEC and 3950 s MELCOR). It is to note that, in this phase, only MELCOR predicts a reverse flow rate through the break (DW pressure plus head of water at the top of DVI major than RPV pressure), ASTEC code predicts the reverse flow later in the transient.

The level in the cavity depends on the a) passive systems injection through the broken DVI (EBT and LGMS), b) the water collected due to the condensation in the containment structure, c) PSS reverse flow, d) break flow rate. In **Figure 7** and **Figure 8** it is represented the normalized level of all the systems that contribute to the cavity level for both codes during the transient.

Figure 7 - Normalized collapsed cavity level, MELCOR

Figure 8 - Normalized collapsed level, ASTEC

The first system activated during the transient is the EBT in MELCOR, at 152 s, while, concerning ASTEC, at 160 s. Subsequently, the complete draining of this system occurs for both codes within the first 500 s of the transient, leading to a sudden rise of the cavity level. This behavior reduces its effectiveness due to the complete draining of the EBT connected to the broken line, but it is sustained by the contribution of the primary side break flow and the subsequent activation of the LGMS system. It is to note that MELCOR predicts a faster level increase in the cavity in the first phase (0s – 500s). Despite the mass flow rate through the break is higher in the ASTEC code, this MELCOR behavior is due to a major condensation in the containment structure. Due to the faster pressure decreases of ASTEC, the LGMS activation took place at 1401 s while in MELCOR at 1888 s. This injection will determine a further increase in the cavity level. In relation to the PSS reverse flow through the vent-pipe, it is to note a higher direct condensation of steam in MELCOR compared to ASTEC in the PSS, that determines a PSS reverse flow in MELCOR at 3010 s, and in ASTEC later at 5534 s. This determines a steeper increase of the cavity level in the MELCOR prediction in comparison with ASTEC and, as shown in **Figure 6**, a slight decrease of the DW pressure calculated by MELCOR. This phenomenon brings to the second equalization of the primary side with the DW and, consequently, to the restart of the break mass flow rate to the cavity earlier in MELCOR as described in the previous section. Therefore, in the MELCOR prediction the level of the cavity reaches the DVI level earlier than ASTEC determining the break reverse flow contributing to increase the level in the core at about 5250 s. Furthermore, the PSS vent injection predicted by the ASTEC code is less sudden than MELCOR calculation but longer over the time.

The level in the core depends on the break flow and the refilling phenomena due to the passive system activation. Initially, the level in the core decreases due to the blowdown. Indeed observing **Figure 9**, at the SOT, it is possible to notice a first decrease of level of both the codes due to the break flow rate.

Figure 9 – a) Normalized collapsed core level, MELCOR; b) normalized collapsed core level, ASTEC;

Table I. Main event characterizing the transient.

Event	MELCOR	ASTEC
Break	0	0
High Containment pressure signal (SCRAM, isolation SG, EHRS activation)	41	20
Low PRZ water level signal (Pump coast down and RI-DC opening)	122	65
Low PRZ pressure signal (ADS Stage-1 opening, EBTs opening)	148	158
Low DP RV-Containment (LGMSs opening)	1884	1398
1 st RPV- DW pressure equalization	2000	1584
2 nd RPV- DW pressure equalization	3315	6006
1 st vent injection	3010	5534
2 nd vent injection	5405	-
Core level reach the TAF	3000	5500
Cavity level reach the DVI	3950	6600
Low LGMS mass (ADS Stage -2 opening)	12265	12902

In MELCOR calculation the lower RPV water level is reached along the EBT injection: the LGMS injection starts at 1888 s and contributes to refill the core. At about 3000 s the level is recovered. After the second equalization in MELCOR it starts again the break flow that determine a small level reduction, but the reverse flow from the break restores again the level, that then remains stable. In relation to ASTEC, the EBT starts to inject at 160 s and affects the level reduction. However, comparing with MELCOR calculation, due to the longer time interval between 1st and 2nd equalization, the EBT stops to inject. While the EBT stops to inject between the two equalizations, the LGMS starts to inject affecting sensibly the level decrease that reaches the minimum at 3000 s. This phenomenon is shown in **Figure 10**; while the EBT system follows the pressure behavior of the primary side, because of the connection balance line between the top of the tank and the upper plenum of the RPV, the LGMS follows the pressure behavior of the PSS tank and, consequently, of the DW. As previously described, during the transient two pressure equalizations occur, in which, after the first equalization, the RPV pressure becomes lower than the DW one. Therefore, during this period, while the EBT stops injecting into the RPV, the LGMS keeps injecting because the higher pressure. The described phenomenon can be observed also in **Figure 6**, in which, between the 1st and the 2nd pressure equalization the level of the EBT does not decrease in both codes and remains constant.

Figure 10 – a) Pressure behavior of DW, PSS, EBT and LGMS, MELCOR; b) Pressure behavior of primary, DW, PSS, EBT and LGMS, ASTEC;

After the 2nd equalization, the LGMS together with the EBT restore the level in the core at about 5500 s. Level restored in both the simulations, the long-term cooling is well predicted by both codes. It is to note that the MELCOR code predicts a minimum normalized level of about 0.6 while ASTEC of about 0.7. The upper part of the core is uncovered in the MELCOR simulation for about 2900 s and in ASTEC for about 5400 s. The maximum cladding temperature predicted by MELCOR and ASTEC is about 622 K and

619 K respectively. No degradation core phenomena are predicted by both codes and no hydrogen is produced.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Within the framework of the Horizon Euratom SASPAM-SA project, the presented code-to-code benchmark exercise between the SA integral system codes MELCOR and ASTEC has been conducted considering a generic iPWR design. It is characterized by a power of about 300 MWe, the adoption of a dry containment and employs several passive systems. The double-ended guillotine break of one of the two DVI lines has been hypothesized as PIE of the DBA sequence. The analysis aimed at studying the thermohydraulic response of both codes and to investigate the discrepancies in terms of the main figure of merits of interest that drive the transients: the primary pressure, the DW pressure, the break flow rate, the level in the cavity and the level in the core. In general, the codes are able to predict the expected dominant phenomena driving the transient but some quantitative discrepancies affecting the sequence of events can be underlined. Of particular interest are the phenomena of condensation in the containment, the heat transfer in the passive heat removal systems and two-phase break flow rate. In particular, MELCOR calculation is characterized by a higher condensation in the containment and by a higher direct condensation in the PSS in comparison with ASTEC. ASTEC code is characterized by a higher heat removal from the passive heat removal systems and a higher two-phase break flow rate. More investigations are currently in progress to characterize these quantitative differences.

NOMENCLATURE

ADS: Automatic Depressurization System; **ASTEC:** Accident Source Term Evaluation Code; **CV:** Control Volume; **DSA:** Deterministic Safety Analysis; **DVI:** Direct Vessel Injection; **DW:** Drywell; **EBT:** Emergency Boration Tank; **EHRS:** Emergency Heat Removal System; **EPZ:** Emergency Planning Zone; **HX:** Heat exChangers; **iPWR:** integral Pressurized Water Reactor; **IRSN:** Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire; **LGMS:** Long-Term Gravity Make-up System; **LOCA:** Loss Of Coolant Accident; **LP:** Lower Plenum; **LWR:** Light Water Reactor; **NPP:** Nuclear Power Plants; **PIE:** Postulated Initiating Event; **PRZ:** Pressurizer; **PSS:** Pressure Suppression System; **QT:** Quench Tank; **RC:** Reactor Cavity; **RCP:** Reactor Coolant Pump; **RCS:** Reactor Cooling System; **RI-DC:** Riser-Downcomer; **RPV:** Reactor Pressure Vessel; **RWST:** Refueling Water Storage Tank; **SA:** Severe Accident; **SASPAM-SA:** Safety Analysis of SMR with Passive Mitigation strategies – Severe Accident; **SBLOCA:** Small Break Loss of Coolant Accident; **SCS:** Secondary Cooling System; **SG:** Steam Generator; **SMR:** Small Modular Reactor; **SNAP:** Symbolic Nuclear Analysis Package; **SNL:** Sandia National Laboratories; **SOT:** Start Of the Transient; **UP:** Upper Plenum; **USNRC:** United States Nuclear Regulatory Commission

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